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Automated Risk Identification In Software Development Using Fuzzy Logic

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ABSTRACT

This study is beneficial to various IT managers, such as Software Users, Software Vendors, research community, IT governance and compliance team and service providers. This will help to speed up risk prediction process, delivery time and reduction of overall cost. The software examines various risk identification techniques. An automated risk identification Model for software development stands as a cornerstone for transforming how software projects manager manages and mitigate risks. The Software development plan and its processes are plagued by different types of risks in the area of personnel involved in the software development, from facility and equipment. Such risks are crashing of hard disk drives, theft and robbery, poor understanding of requirements and others. An experiment with IT and software engineering participants demonstrated how the traditional method works, revealing that risk identification took 58 minutes on average, with RAM development taking 30 minutes and 45 seconds. These results highlighted the traditional method's inefficiency. Therefore, this study entails developing an Enhanced Risk Analysis Model - ERAM) for identifying, determining and prognosis of risk emanating from tasks and resources which are associated with software development. The method used includes examining time usage for risk identification in the traditional method, followed by designing the Enhanced Risk Analysis Model (ERAM). The ERAM was developed to improve this process, using trapezoidal membership functions to categorize tasks by difficulty and risk, considering project factors such as human resources and task complexity. Fuzzy logic principles were used to analyze tasks and compute fuzzy sets for resources and time, creating a resource-time matrix that categorized tasks into different difficulty levels, providing a more efficient risk assessment compared to the traditional method. The proposed ERAM is a supportive tool for risk identification and classification based on its "two level sieve"- the conditional probability and the fuzzy logic as a classification tool which makes it difficult for any threat converting to risk without being captured. This study is beneficial to various IT managers, software users, Software Vendors, research community, IT governance and compliance team and service providers. This will speed up risk prediction process, delivery time and reduction of overall cost.

Keywords: Risk predictive model; risk identification techniques; Enhanced Risk Analysis model (ERAM); Risk Mitigation; Fuzzy logic;

1. 0 INTRODUCTION

Businesses, banking sector, educational system, phones, home gadgets, cars and houses have been made smart and are being controlled by software [1]. Based on this reality, there is need for quality software used by most businesses, basic home appliances, security and modern civilization. To attain quality in software development, a range of possible factors such as the process that births the software, the choice of models used, formation and motivation of the teams involved in the development, delivery time, handling of risks and risk areas must all come to play. Amongst these factors needed to attain quality, the

choice of process models in relation to how risks are handled is a major determinant of quality and quick delivery of software; and these two are inevitable entities in the developmental process [2].

Risk is an uncertainty or set of events that if allowed to occur, will have adverse or negative effect on the software development process or the quality of the end product (Office of Government Commerce, 2013).

Risk is not limited to location of the software project, the time spent planning or how advance the resources are, it could happen anywhere and at any time during the software development life cycle [3]

Software risks are events that may or may not take place; ones which results in negative consequences on the software project as a whole [2] The risk may affect some or all the aspect of the development; such as the planning, the tools (technology), staffing and financing.

1.1 Related Works

A Risk Management Model is a mechanism that enables the implementation of a particular risk analysis method. A range of different method and existing models have been used in the past either to identify, assess or predict risk. Some of the basic techniques used in identifying and solving problem in software projects include but not limited to six thinking hat, nine boxes, brainstorming, risk checklist, prompt lists, risk breakdown structure [4], Society for Human Resource Management [5]. While the more elaborate ones are the “Boehm’s risk management model sometimes called spiral models. Software Engineering Institute Continuous Risk Management (SEI-CRM) method and Kontio’s Riskit method” [6]; [7]; [2],

[2] emphasized the role and the importance of a great and excellent team in the software development process. Stressing that team collaboration is a critical factor to reaching the set-out objectives; which means that team formation is one of the risky tasks in the software project. Again, were these participants communicated their different rights before or during the survey? Nothing was mentioned of the biased results! How were they handled? All these need to be improved on [2].

Software development presents many strategic opportunities but also plagued with equal level of uncertainties and since in most cases development and overhead costs are irrecoverable, it is therefore necessary to device means of managing the uncertainties. The major focus of this work was to “demonstrate, through literature and current technology review, the need for intelligent and adaptive tools for risk management. Analysis of the framework of “Software Engineering Institute (SEI)’s Software Risk Management (SRM) Methodologies, Capability Maturity Model Integration (CMMI) and the Project Management Body of Knowledge (PMBOK)” and the two approaches to risk (and or project) management were presented. Though, having outlined the Risk analysis process and the elements present in it; the authors presented the need for intelligent risk management tools through the Neural Network approach. However, the work only presented the needs for intelligent tools by proposing two frame works namely: “neural networks and intelligent agent based”, no design or structural model was used to help understand their work. Hence, the need to be improved on [2]

Yoro (2025) explored the use of machine learning (ML) models such as Random Forests, SVMs, and Naïve Bayes, and also deep learning (DL) networks such as RNN, CNN, and LSTM to detect DDoS attacks in Software-Defined Networking (SDN) contexts. The study shows that ML models often deliver quick and explicit performance, they can plateau and be less effective on complex data. DL methods with its depth and flexibility, bring stronger representational strength but come with downsides. Findings show that Random Forests, SVMs, and Naïve Bayes approaches combining multiple classifiers can significantly improve detection accuracy. Yoro (2025)

The CMMI (Capability Maturity Model Integration), Microsoft Solutions Framework (MSF) Risk Management Model, the IEEE risk management standards, and Collaborative Risk Management. The work then identified and analyzed the multi-characters of software risks to include: “multi-stages, multi-objective, uncertainty, multi-methods, multi-dimensions, multi-attributes and multi-objects”. In the subsequent sections, automated risk management tools which uses WEKA for its data mining was introduced to help managers to make decision on the issues relating to software risks. Some prediction model such as 9K-near neighbor approach, ID3 decision tree and the Neural Network were also identified with SVM being the dominant algorithm. However, it is expected that detailed risk factors which may include major problem areas in software projects is listed first before grouping them under major

headings (which was later used). As a result of the grouped headings used, the risk factors used in the data set is minimal. This may have influenced the result gotten at the end of the day [9]; [10].

[11] Used an improve Bayesian model for accurate risk prediction in software projects. Authors' argument was based on the fact that the accuracy of the existing published models is limited (for some reasons). Hence, the work began with an analysis of some existing models like the defect prediction model, the mechanism of the “dynamic discretization algorithm” and the “Revised software project risk models”. Based on the output generated from each of these models after simulation, a comparison was made and then conclusion drawn on the behavior of each of the model used for different test. Although, each of the model were said to have been used for different test, one would hope that there would be a major (or separate) benchmark for assessing the performance of the developed models. Authors' proposition of an integrated model from the existing two developed in the MODIST project is also a welcome development. This process with the incorporation of other critical factors that may influence the software development process into the integrated model will further reveal the capability of the models against planned or proposed integrated model [11].

[12] study on data misuse and theft protection model in internet of things devices review that, exponential growth of the Internet of Things (IoT) has significantly transformed daily human activities by developing an interconnected ecosystem of people, devices, data, and digital processes, but also introduces numerous security and privacy concerns. The research designed an algorithm that will secure data and create hierarchy to access information within its focus The results revealed that IoT devices are seen to be vulnerable due to limited computational resources, its weak authentication protocols, and inadequate encryption standards.

[13] work review that rapid evolution of digital technology has greatly influenced consumers' behavior, especially in the area of online and mobile commerce. The study emphasized importance of consumer knowledge, perceived advantages, and quality service in driving internet adoption. As mobile technologies continue to reshape sectors such as education, communication, and finance, mobile commerce, however, despite the global growth of mobile-based services adoption in developing countries, including Nigeria, remains relatively sluggish. He stressed that the application of integrative theoretical models like the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM), Diffusion of Innovation (DOI), Expectation Confirmation Theory (ECT), and the Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT), which collectively explore user behavior from multiple dimensions ranging from perceived ease of use to social influence. The work applied the theories within the Nigerian telecommunications sector to assess consumer attitudes toward virtual airtime and e-voucher usage. Its findings revealed that role of socio-technical factors in promoting the shift toward a cashless economy and support the notion that tailored interventions are necessary to encourage consistent digital engagement in developing regions, it highlighted how cultural, infrastructural, and socioeconomic factors often hinder widespread adoption in such contexts. [13]

[14] study on investigates the risks and financial losses merchants face during failed cash-on-delivery (COD) e-commerce transactions. Questionnaires was distributed across major online retail platforms—such as Jumia, Konga, PayPorte, Slot.ng, and Jiji Nigeria—the research identifies key risk factors tied to COD failures including return shipments, extra packaging and unpacking efforts, logistical challenges, and others. The study proposes a *Centralized Merchant Registration Retrieval (CMRR)* model. The model leverages a post-billing mechanism to deduct a nominal fee from customers, it was designed to offset the costs related to unsuccessful COD deliveries. The research shows the operational, and financial challenges associated with COD transactions, such as high return rates, logistical inefficiencies, substantial burdens on e-commerce businesses and revenue losses from failed deliveries. The model aims to redistribute risk by holding customers partially accountable for transaction failures, show strong support from merchants, consumer hesitancy and persistent concerns over post-payment trust and transparency. [14]

[15] findings revealed that Support Vector Machines can effectively model complex traffic patterns and can be integrated into intelligent transportation systems to improve traffic flow and reduce congestion. The study also discusses the implications of these predictions for urban planning and the development of

smart city initiatives. Machine learning techniques, particularly supervised learning algorithms such as Support Vector Machines (SVM), were explored for the effectiveness in modeling complex traffic dynamics. SVM's ability to handle high-dimensional data and nonlinear relationships makes it suitable for forecasting vehicle trajectories and traffic patterns. The integration of such data allows for comprehensive traffic analysis and real-time prediction capabilities. The study used Validation metrics to demonstrate high accuracy, supporting SVM's applicability in practical traffic management contexts. Moreover, the use of machine learning for vehicular prediction aligns with broader smart city initiatives focused on optimizing urban mobility through data-driven solutions. Accurate movement forecasting assists in proactive traffic control, infrastructure planning, and resource allocation.

[16] developed a system that addressed challenges such as insufficient infrastructure, cash handling inefficiencies, and inappropriate data management by integrating modern digital payment system and inventories control features. The finding shows that, design and implementation of an enhanced point of sales (POS) system particularly for retail businesses in developing countries, improved transaction speed, accuracy, and customer satisfaction, emphasizing the system's potential to boost retail efficiency in resource-constrained environments. [16]

[17] work on the impact of Cash Scarcity on adoption of Banking technology by Consumers, used survey data to investigate how cash scarcity influences consumers patronage on adoption of banking technologies in Delta State. Using survey data, the study finds that effect of cash unavailability significantly drives consumers towards digital banking platforms, mobile money, and other electronic payment systems. The results emphasize the need for all banks to enhance technological accessibility, availability and awareness to support financial inclusion during cash shortages.

[18] work on consumer preference, intentions and trust on Purchasing-pattern for online Virtual Shops explores consumer behavior as regarding online virtual shops, it focuses on preferences, purchase intentions of the customers, and trust factors. The study used questionnaire-based data, and findings reveals that trust-building mechanisms and user-friendly interfaces positively impact buying decisions. The study offers insights into optimizing e-commerce platforms to better align with consumer expectations and enhance online shopping experiences. [18]

[19] work revealed an improved techniques for detecting malicious websites through applying data balancing techniques to a Random Forest integrated model. The results produced shows and validate the model's robustness in identifying phishing and malware sites, adding to safer internet navigations. The concept effectively addresses class imbalance in cybersecurity datasets, enhancing detection accuracy and reducing false positives.

[20] work on improving Customers trust through fraud prevention E-commerce Model developed a fraud prevention model and aimed at increasing customer trust in e-commerce platforms. By integrating real-time fraud detection algorithms and secure transaction protocols, the model reduces fraudulent activities immediately they occur and enhances users' confidence. The case studies indicate that designing, integrating and implementing this model will lead to higher customer retention and improved subsequent online business credibility.

[21] study on comparative data Resample to Predict Subscription Services attrition using Tree-based Ensembles results shows that a particular resampling approach combined with ensemble algorithms will greatly improve prediction accuracy and precision. It aids early identification of churn-prone customers. The research compared various data resampling techniques for predicting customers attrition in subscription services using tree-based ensemble methods, enabling proactive retention strategies. [21]

[22] work checkmate and explore the impact of different data resampling methods on customer churn prediction using Random Forest and XGBoost classifiers. The research findings show that balancing imbalanced datasets substantially improve model performance, with XGBoost significantly outperforming Random Forest in churn detection. The study provides practical methods for data scientists working on customer retention analytics. Aghware (2024)

[23] study on Application of Recency Frequency Model (RFM) on Customer Segmentation in Digital Marketing indicated and shown how RFM segmentation helps marketers utilize and tailor personalized strategies, optimize resource allocation, and increase campaign effectiveness. The Recency, Frequency,

and Monetary (RFM) model was applied to segment customers in digital marketing campaigns. Through empirical analysis, the model proves valuable for improving customer targeting and engagement.

[24] work developed a blockchain-based framework to combat the circulation of counterfeit drugs in the pharmaceutical supply chain. The adoption of blockchain technology framework for Addressing Counterfeit drugs circulation decentralized and tamper-proof nature of blockchain enhances drug traceability, authenticity verification, and stakeholder transparency. Findings based on the implementation of blockchain-based framework indicates a promising reduction in counterfeit incidents and improved patient safety.

[25] Ojugo, the study introduces CoSoGMIR, a novel social graph contagion diffusion framework that models information spread based on human movement, interaction, and return behaviors. The concept improves accuracy in predicting contagion dynamics within social networks, with applications in epidemiology, marketing, and information dissemination.

[26] developed a machine learning-based automated risk identification model for financial fraud detection. Their model utilized decision trees and random forest algorithms to classify financial transactions with high accuracy. The results demonstrated a promising ability to flag anomalous patterns indicating potential fraud. However, the model was trained on a relatively narrow dataset from a single financial institution, limiting its generalizability to broader contexts. The study also failed to address real-time processing capabilities, which are critical in high-frequency transaction environments. Moreover, the model's interpretability was

1.2 Problem Formulation:

The Software development plan and its processes are plagued by different types of risks. There are several risk management methods and techniques that have been developed in the past to help with risk and risk areas of software project processes. However, none of these methods is designed to surpass others during full implementation.

Automating the tasks and resources based in the risk identification phase (or stage) of the generic process will help ease the work load involved in the whole process. To this end, this work developed a model (an adaptable form of Risk analysis method called Enhanced Risk Analysis Model - ERAM) which would be used for identifying and prognosis of risk emanating from tasks and resources in software development projects.

2.0 METHODOLOGY

The methodology and procedure for the practical design and implementation of the automated risk identification model:

[4] method was adopted in the design and implementation of this research work. [4] model which focuses on using Enhanced Fuzzy Induction Models for Software Requirement Risk Prediction, to stratify and analyze causal risk factors by applying logistic regression as a statistical tool for controlling the software development process. This work also built upon the research on prediction of risk factors in software development projects using multiple logistic regression which was out by [11]. This model aimed to stratify and analyze causal risk factors by applying logistic regression as a statistical tool for controlling the software development process. The risk classification was derived from factor analysis and logistic regression, which predicted the likelihood of project success or failure with a reported accuracy of 90%.

- The main development tools used during the research and in the development of the system as a whole are: Python programming language, Fuzzy logic (skfuzzy library), Scikit-learn (machine learning models), Pandas and NumPy (data processing), Matplotlib, Seaborn, and Plotly (data visualization), Streamlit (web-based user interface), Visual Studio Code (development environment)
- To create a baseline for comparison, a real-life experiment was conducted to measure the time and effort required by the Generic method. Participants, consisting of experts from computer science and Information Technology, used brainstorming and checklist techniques to identify risk factors.

- The process involved identifying factors, defining action plans, and generating a risk table. The time taken for each step was recorded. The risk table included headings such as risk items, risk category, components affected, probability, impact, and RMMM (Risk Monitoring, Management, and Mitigation). Over fifteen initial points were generated and consolidated into seven distinct risk items.

Risk Management

Risk management is the act of identification through full assessment of the software project and managing the risks identified in order to pre-empt, alleviate or control them [27]. Risk Management is a continuous process which begins at the planning phase of the project, and continues all through the project life cycle. The aim as presented is to identify, address and eliminate problem areas before they can cause any damage in the project process. As deduced from SMART-Consortium (2021), most software risks are assessed in line with project goals and objectives. Usually, most risk management techniques uses four main perspectives [28]. . The strategic, operational, program and project perspectives. The methodology used in risk management may be common across all the four perspectives, however risk management procedure must be tailored to suit each one. The actual management process is performed based on four phases as analyzed below.

2.1 Risk Management Phases

The phases or stages of software risk management are [29]; [30]; [31]:

- i. Identification phase
- ii. Quantitative assessment phase
- iii. Define an alternative phase (Risk mitigation phase)
- iv. Monitoring and control phase

I Identification Phases

Identification of risk areas with the aid of a well-structured and consistent method to make sure all software development project areas are captured and adequately addressed. Risk identification phase involves activities such as searching and listing out all the risks in a software development project, logging and classification of all the risks found. Depending on type of project and how identification is done, risk identification phase can be divided into three categories [32]. Identification could be done by risk analyst based on his capacity, knowledge and experience acquired in practice; It could also be done through interview conducted by risk analyst plus one or many members of the software project team and identification could be done by one or many members of the software project team under the guidance and directive of the risk analyst.

[19] discussed further several techniques for identifying risks. These techniques include: Delphi Technique, brainstorming, use of Influence Diagram, Interview or Expert Judgment, Checklist, Nominal Group Technique, Flowcharts or Graphical notations, Pondering, Root Cause Identification, Cause-and-Effect Diagrams, Questionnaire, SWOT Analysis (“strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats”), Synectic, Case Based Approach, Electronic Brainstorming, Business Impact Analysis. In this work, a combination of fuzzy classification and case based is used [33].

II Quantitative Assessment

After Identification, the next stage is to carry out a quantitative assessment of the risk and then rank risk items to know or confirm those that needs urgent attention. In [34], risk assessments were done to evaluate strength and weakness of software risk assessment tools, Software risk assessment is defined as the process of identifying, analyzing, and prioritizing risks in the software development project. The following are some of the tools used for assessing risks in software development [34].

- a) CMMI Quantitative approach
- b) Probabilistic inference model
- c) Fuzzy logic based
- d) Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP) and Support Vector Regression (SVR)

It also yields an excellent guideline for risk assessment to include:

1. Assess the probability of occurrence of risk.
2. Assess impact of risk occurring (that is, if it eventually occurs).

3. Define (or set) suitable risk quadrant.
4. Assess the Stakeholders that are involved as well as the depth of their involvement.
5. Define risk priority.

III Define an alternative path (Risk mitigation)

According to [34] the next and the third step is to decide on an alternative path or define a response plan to alleviate or minimize risk and also set conditions to initiate or terminate these alternate activities. Basically, a four-step approaches could be applied as a mitigation plan [34].

- a. Avoid risk where possible by eliminating threat and problem as soon as possible.
- b. Make plan for mitigation incase where avoidance is inapplicable
- c. Accept and budget for contingency
- d. Outsource the responsibility of management.

IV Plan for Monitoring and control

The last phase or step for risk management is to make adequate and strong plans for monitoring and controlling of risks throughout the entire lifespan of the project with clear definitions, review and reassessment of milestone. The monitoring requires constant discipline of executions. It involves executing the planned monitoring and control strategies, constant evaluation of plans and proper documentation [35]. The risk management specialist often applies these steps to ensure that nothing goes wrong during development process. However, implementing risk management methods is still not popular due to the following reasons.

- a. Risk is an abstract concept.
- b. Providing accurate estimates for probability and loss is not usually easy.
- c. Risks have different implications to different stakeholders.
- d. Each risk may affect a project in more than one way.
- e. Many of the risks management methods are multifaceted (or complex) and costly to use.

2.2 Risk Management Tools

Using tools is a major way of identifying and managing risks in software project. Automated tools may be used to store, organize and process raw data into very meaningful information. Examples of readily available tools for risk management in software project are: Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP), Support Vector Regression (SVR), Risk Assessment Visualization Tool (RAVT), fuzzy Logic, Probabilistic Inference Mode, Capacity Maturity Model Integration (CMMI) Quantitative Approach. Most risk management tools are developed or implemented using different application development platforms, however, at different level of risk management these tools can be applied to suit the purpose of the user [2].

2.3 Existing Risk Management Models

A Risk Management Model is a mechanism that enables the implementation of a particular risk analysis method. A range of different method and existing models have been used in the past either to identify, assess or predict risk areas in a software development project. Some of the basic techniques used in identifying and solving problem in software projects include but not limited to six thinking hat, nine boxes, brainstorming, risk checklist, prompt lists, risk breakdown structure [4]; Society for Human Resource Management [31]. While the more elaborate ones are the “Boehm’s risk management model sometimes called spiral models. Software Engineering Institute Continuous Risk Management (SEI-CRM) method and Kontio’s Riskit method” [2].

Aside the traditional or generic models, there are several other risk management models that have either been proposed or evolved based on the traditional models or a hybrid of two or more models. As presented in [23] these models include; “The Soft-risk model, Hall of software risk management process, Software Engineering Institute (SEI)’s Software Risk Management (SRM) Information Technology Systems risk management methodology, Thomsett risk management process, SERIM (Software Engineering Risk Index Management) method of Karolak, and Pro-Risk framework developed by Roy”. [36]; [37]; .

2.3.1 The Software Engineering Institute (SEI)'s Software Risk Management (SRM) Model

The SEI's SRM methodologies is supported by three groups of practices. These are: the Software Risk Evaluation (SRE), Continuous Risk Management (CRM) and Team Risk Management (TRM) [35]; [6]. The framework was developed to enable engineers, project managers, other stakeholders and decision makers to identify, early enough “all the risks associated with software acquisition, development, integration, and deployment so that appropriate management and mitigation strategies can be developed on a timely basis”, [33]. The main objectives of this risk management method are to:

- I. Prevent risk occurrence
- II. mitigate risk and effect correction where necessary
- III. Ensure safe system failure.

To achieve these three objectives, Open communication, Teamwork, Global perspective, Shared product vision and Forward-looking view are some of the management principles which had been instrumental to it. The SRE defined five major stages for risk management with directly maps with the SDLC phases. These stages are shown in figure 1

Figure 1 The SRE five stages of risk management (Fragulis *et al.*, 2021).

2.4 High level Architecture of the model

In this work a framework which develop and implement the machine learning algorithm power and risk analysis automated model with time dependent. It shows a high level of view of the new algorithm with the main component of the system, and services the algorithm providers how they communicate (see Figure 2). The algorithm is implemented using two architecture that comprises code that involves different task section and result after running the code section,

Figure 2 High level Architecture of the purpose System (Ugbome, 2024)

3.0 Data Prep-processing

To arrive at the decision as to whether a task is difficult or not, the [26] data was analyzed to obtain information on:

- Different tasks available
- The period taken to carry out an average task, for example., coding hour, interface design, etc,
- Human experts involved in project process
- Other project operation

These data informed our decision of parameters used for the fuzzy aspect of our system to classify task from resource and to adequately predict level of task difficulty or easiness at each stage (or task sub-segment) of development through average time spent on stages in comparison to resources category per hour.

3.1 Evaluating Enhance Risk Automation model

ERAM utilizes a fuzzy logic system to handle ambiguity in input parameters like task difficulty and resource availability. The output variable W_i represents the assessed difficulty or risk level of a task, with the following interpretations:

- Output $W_i = 0$:** It simply indicate the Extreme case of task easiness. The task has all resources at its disposal with no contention.
- Output $W_i = 0.25$:** A "very easy" task, likely requiring only a single, readily available resource.
- Output $W_i = 0.5$:** An "easy" task. It may require more than one resource, but they are available without significant delay.
- Output $W_i = 0.75$:** This shows an inclination, which means that the task is "considerably difficult" and may take time to complete.

- **Output $W_i = 0.9 - 1.0$:** The negative extreme, indicating a "very difficult" task. The project is at risk, as the task may be delayed due to resource contention or other blocking issues.

3.2 Design of the Enhance Risk Analysis Model (ERAM)

The Enhanced Risk Analysis Model (ERAM) is designed to integrate seamlessly into the software development process, focusing on task and resource-based risk identification and prognosis. The algorithm follows a structured, multi-step approach.

Inputs:

- Project Plan, Task List, Resource List
- Historical Data on Previous Projects
- Risk Categories and Risk Factors
- Stakeholder Requirements and Constraints

Outputs:

- Identified Risks
- Risk Prioritization and Scoring
- Mitigation Strategies
- Monitoring and Control Plan

The algorithm proceeds through seven steps: Initialization, Risk Identification, Risk Assessment, Risk Prioritization, Risk Mitigation Planning, Implementation and Monitoring, and Review and Improvement. The core of ERAM is a machine learning model trained to classify and assess risk from project data. Four different algorithms were evaluated, with Random Forest and Gradient Boosting demonstrating superior performance, both achieving an accuracy of 96.67%.

Testing Methods

No single testing type is sufficient for a complex system. Therefore, a combination of techniques was employed, with a focus on the dynamic method of testing. This particular method of testing was chosen because the system is a modular and requires test data to verify the functionality of its individual units or parts, before they were integrated to form the whole System. Table 1 shows the time spent on identifying risks in software project development manually and total time spent as a whole, while Table 2 shows the total time spent on identifying risk in a software development project

Table 1: Time Spent on Manual Risk Table Generation (Brainstorming)

Risk Table Headings	Description/Points Identified	Total Time Spent (minutes)
Risk Items Identified	Wrong choice of process model, Inappropriate IDE, Lack of Knowledge, etc.	14
Risk Categories	Technical, Process/Project, Business, etc.	6
Components Affected	Quality, Performance, Time, Cost	11
Probability	Calculated from initial Risk Probability Impact (RPI)	14
Impact	Assigned weight to risk (1–10) and calculated	8
RMMM	Risk Monitoring, Management & Mitigation	5
Total Time Spent		58 minutes

Total time spent on producing RAM and reaching a conclusion

Following the brainstorming, a Risk Analysis Model (RAM) was generated for a single factor to measure the time for this granular analysis.

Table 2: Time Spent on Manual RAM Generation (For a Single Factor)

Entity	Number Considered	Time Spent
Factor (F)	1	45 seconds
Event (Ev)	3	12 minutes
Reaction (R)	3	11 minutes
Effect (E)	3	7 minutes
Total RAM Time		30 minutes 45 seconds

As shown in the Table 2, the combined time for the manual Generic Risk analysis process for a limited set of risks was approximately **89 minutes**.

4. Result Variations

It is important to state that there may be variations to the result above. This is primarily due to the fact that it is not possible to have the same number of sets for the components represented in the RAM. For instance, the event set may have four sets, while the reaction set may be five. The results of the manual process are also inherently subjective and can be influenced by the participants’ cognitive state, experience, and potential biases.

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Table 3: Performance Metrics of Machine Learning Models

Model	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1-Score
Random Forest	0.9667	0.9677	0.9667	0.9663
Gradient Boosting	0.9667	0.9672	0.9667	0.9663
SVM	0.7889	0.8033	0.7889	0.7635
Neural Network	0.8111	0.8282	0.8111	0.8141

Time Efficiency: As detailed in Tables 2 and Table 3, the Generic method required a total of 89 minutes. In stark contrast, ERAM performed the equivalent analysis in under one minute of execution time

Figure 3: Machine Learning Model Evaluation

Enhanced Risk Analysis Model (ERAM)

Software Development Risk Analysis using ML & Fuzzy Logic

Generic Riskit vs ERAM Benchmarking

Run Benchmark Analysis

Benchmark analysis completed!

Delivery Time Prediction Accuracy

ERAM MAE
1.37 days

Generic Riskit MAE
1.94 days

ERAM Improvement
29.5%
↑ 29.5%

Generic Riskit vs ERAM Performance Comparison

Figure 4: Generic Riskit vs ERAM Benchmarking

5.0 CONCLUSION

The design of the proposed model revealed that software development processes or tasks are saddled with various types of risk. Task duration and resources allocation are two major software project parameters that should be managed properly if risk areas are to be identified early

Risk management is a very important consideration in software and Information technology projects as a whole. Although in this work, attention has been on how risk is identified in a major risk model – called generic riskit model however, several other aspects of risks such as the definition, types and categories, management, prediction models, how to mitigate or alleviate risk were covered as we narrowed down on the major topic and finally draw a conclusion on timing and quality of product.

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